

Analyzing Mortality Risk of COVID-19 Patients Using Machine Learning

Sreya M

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, India
sreyam2022b@mca.ajce.in

T J Jobin

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, India
tjjobin@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— The abrupt increase in the number of illnesses and high fatality rates during the covid-19 epidemic have put enormous strain on public health services. As a result, identifying the main parameters for mortality prediction is essential for improving patient treatment plans. Early detection of patient mortality issues can help to avert death by ensuring optimal resource allocation and treatment planning. The primary goal of this research is to swiftly identify the Severe Covid-19 patient by looking at demographics, comorbidities, admission, laboratory data, admission medicines, admission oxygen therapy prescriptions, discharge, and mortality data. Various machine learning models (linear regression, decision trees, and KNN) were trained and their performance compared to determine the model that consistently achieves high accuracy during the disease's days.

Keywords—machine learning, feature selection algorithms, accuracy metrics, tuning

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning is a type of artificial intelligence (AI) that makes systems to learn from their mistakes and enhance without having to be explicitly programmed. The data or observations (examples or instructions) are necessary for the process of machine learning.

It looks for patterns in data and then provide conclusions based on the examples provided. In this study various data such as medicine, oxygen therapy, laboratory data are used to obtain the result . Feature selection algorithms are used to select the best features. Three machine learning models used in this study are Decision tree, KNN algorithms and Linear Regression. These models are compared using its accuracy score are results the best models.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

[A] Michael Rieder, Mahdi Mahdavi, Hadi Choubdar, Erfan ZabehID, Mahdi Mahdavi-“A machine learning based exploration of COVID-19 mortality risk”. This study develops and compares the machine learning models for predicting. The prediction is based on the medical and statical data obtained at the time of patient’s admission. Models used to compare are three SVM models.

[B] Mario A. Quiroz-Juárez, Armando Torres-Gómez, Irma Hoyo-Ulloa, Roberto de J. León-Montiel, and Alfred B. U’Ren - “Identification of high-risk COVID-19 patients using machine learning”. In this study, detect the covid –19 patients with high risk using machine learning. So the emergency department can provide the specialized care. This technique quickly identify the critical patients.

[C] Akshaya Karthikeyan , Akshit Garg , P. K. Vinod and U. Deva Priyakumar-Machine Learning Based Clinical Decision Support System for Early COVID-19 Mortality Prediction. This study discovered a powerful five-feature combination that helps predict COVID-19 patient death reliably. Various ml algorithms have been created to contrast and forecast mortality with the greatest accuracy.

[D] Erwin Cornelius , Olcay Akman , and Dan Hrozencik-COVID-19 Mortality Prediction Using Machine Learning-Integrated Random Forest Algorithm under Varying Patient Frailty. This study predict COVID-19 patient death using statics information from patients in the US. The Random Forest approach is a well-known machine learning methodology that had already been utilised to achieve comparable objectives. In fact, when compared to a variety of other algorithms, the AdaBoost enhanced random forest was found to provide greater predictive performance..

III. METHODOLOGY

Jupyter Notebook is used as an IDE in this prediction analysis. It's an open-source platform with a variety of modules and visualization capabilities. This interface uses many graph plots to show the data in the dataset. It's possible to compare the data fields within a dataset. Seaborn, sklearn, Matplotlib, NumPy and other modules are used in Jupyter.

Fig.1 Outline of Jupyter notebook

A. Requirements

- Jupyter Notebook
- .csv dataset
- Decision Tree Algorithm
- KNN Algorithm
- Linear Regression Algorithm

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B. Decision Tree

The decision tree is the most effective and widely used categorization and prediction tool. Each internal node represents an attribute test, each leaf node (terminal node) stores a category name, and each branch represents a test result in a tree-like structure that resembles a flowchart. Decision Trees are a supervised non-parametric learning method that can be used for classification and regression.

C. Linear Regression

Linear Regression is type of technique used for supervised learning in machine learning. It does a regression task. Regression models with a goal prediction value were made possible by using independent variables. It's commonly used to figure out how factors interact and predict outcomes. Different regression models allow for varied types of dependent and independent variable associations, as well as different amounts of independent variables.

D. KNN Algorithms

The K-Nearest Neighbour approach, is a Supervised Learning technique, is one of the most sophisticated Machine Learning algorithms available. The K-NN technique is predicated on the assumption that the present case/data and past cases are comparable, and it allocates the new case to the most similar category to the existing categories. The K-NN method saves all available data and replaces it with a value that is close to it. As fresh data is received, it will be quickly sorted into the appropriate category using the K-NN algorithm.

IV. DATASET

The implementation of prediction covid 19 patients mortality risk has based on a set of datasets. The.csv file extension is used to save the data.It is a collection of data used for analysis. The dataset contains different columns and corresponding variables. The dataset is from Kaggle.com

AE	AF	AG	AH	AI	AJ	AK	AL	AM	AN	AO	AP	AQ	AR	AS	AT
0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Fig.2.Dataset for prediction analysis

V. IMPLEMENTATION

Firstly, Download and install the latest python version, then install jupyter notebook through command prompt. Then open the Jupyter Notebook using jupyter notebook command in command prompt. Create a new file by selecting New.

```

In [ ]: # Import Libraries
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import os
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from pandas import ExcelFile
from pandas import ExcelWriter

# Use this in Jupyter notebooks to display static images inline
%matplotlib inline

from pandas_profiling import ProfileReport
import category_encoders as ce
import graphviz

# preprocessing
import sklearn
from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder, StandardScaler, MinMaxScaler, RobustScaler
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split, GridSearchCV, RandomizedSearchCV, StratifiedKFold, learning_curve, ShuffleSplit
from sklearn.metrics import cross_val_predict as cvp
from sklearn import metrics

from sklearn.metrics import r2_score, mean_absolute_error, mean_squared_error, accuracy_score, confusion_matrix, explained_variance_ratio_
from sklearn.feature_selection import VarianceThreshold
from sklearn.feature_selection import SelectKBest, SelectFromModel

# models
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression, LogisticRegression, Perceptron, RidgeClassifier, SGDClassifier, LinearSVC
from sklearn.svm import SVC, LinearSVC, SMO
from sklearn.ensemble import BoostingClassifier, GradientBoostingClassifier, ExtraTreesClassifier, RandomForestClassifier
from sklearn.ensemble import BaggingClassifier, AdaBoostClassifier, VotingClassifier
from sklearn.ensemble import StackingClassifier
from sklearn.naive_bayes import GaussianNB
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier
from sklearn.gaussian_process import GaussianProcessClassifier
from sklearn.neural_network import MLPClassifier
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier, plot_tree, export_graphviz
from sklearn import metrics
    
```

Fig.3 Import the libraries.

Derivation	LOS	LOS Death	Age	Severity	Black	White	Asian	Latino	Ferritin	C-reactive	C-reactive	Procalcitonin	Procalcitonin	Procalcitonin	Troponin	Troponin
0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Fig.4 Import the dataset

```

main_features_of = main_features_opt.nlargest(num_features_opt, 'max').index.tolist()
if not 'Death' in main_features:
    main_features.append('Death')
main_features
    
```

Fig.5. Select the 35 most common features from the feature set using feature selection algorithms

Then splitting data into train data and test data. Since our problem is Supervised Machine Learning Classification Problem. So, we can use Linear Regression, KNN Algorithm and Decision Tree Classifier and Select the Best Algorithm from these which gives best result on Test dataset.

Fig.10. Confusion matrix Using Decision tree

```
{'n_neighbors': 9}
Unique values in y_test and their count: (array([0, 1]), array([875, 303]))
Unique values in y_pred_test and their count: (array([0, 1]), array([1049,
-----
y_train = [0 1 0 1 0]
y_pred_train = [0 0 0 1 0]
x_test = [0 0 0 0 1]
y_pred_test = [0 0 0 1 0]
acc of r2_score for train = 0.92
acc of r2_score for test = -17.3
acc of acc for train = 81.97
acc of acc for test = 77.59
acc of rmse for train = 42.46
acc of rmse for test = 47.34
acc of re for train = 75.38
acc of re for test = 87.13
-----TRAIN DATA-----
Best threshold: 0.22
Accuracy of train model: 0.76
Precision : 0.96
Recall : 0.72
f1_score : 0.82
AUC_score : 0.89
-----TEST DATA-----
Best threshold: 0.22
Accuracy of test model: 0.7
Precision : 0.89
Recall : 0.69
f1_score : 0.77
AUC_score : 0.78
```

Fig.9. Accuracy of KNN

VI. RESULT

From the above analysis, we got the prediction accuracy of three models and from this Linear regression has nearly identical performance on the test set and train set. So Linear regression can give the best result on the identification of mortality risk on covid-19 patients.

Prediction accuracy for models

	Model	acc_train	acc_test	acc_diff
1	Decision Tree Classifier	85.28	80.98	4.30
2	KNN	81.97	77.59	4.38
0	Linear Regression	77.21	74.79	2.42

VII. CONCLUSION

Forecasting mortality prediction is critical during the COVID-19 pandemic because it can help us minimize disease death rates by determining where and how to respond. In COVID-19 patients who were hospitalized, demographics, comorbidities, admission, laboratory findings, admission medicines, admission supplementary oxygen prescriptions, discharge, and mortality data were all found to be substantially related with an increased risk of death. To optimise patient treatment and results, healthcare providers should discover these characteristics at the moment of diagnosis. In a range of scenarios, the models showed the best prediction performance, making them effective tools for medical decision-making and allocation of resources. Future research could concentrate on specific groups of comorbidities and additional variables in order to construct alternative models.

VIII. REFERENCES

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